

Enhancing Multiclass Image Classification Accuracy through Transfer Learning: A Study on Convolutional Neural Network

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Abstract: Deep convolutional neural network (CNN) architectures play a crucial role in enhancing image classification performance, particularly when dealing with complex foregrounds and similarities between images from different classes. While deep neural networks have proven effective in practical applications requiring high accuracy and low regression coefficients, they cannot entirely replace human involvement. This research paper aims to increase the accuracy of multiclass image classification by leveraging transfer learning in conjunction with fine-tuning techniques to enhance the performance of respective CNN models. Specifically, the VGG19, ResNet50, InceptionV3, and Xception CNN architectures are evaluated for image classification tasks. Our proposed approach focuses on optimizing pretrained CNN models using a preprocessing technique that involves image enhancement. Mean normalization and resizing techniques are applied to images from each class, which are further augmented using diverse data augmentation methods. To prevent overfitting, dropout regularization and an early stopping function are employed. The ADAM (Adaptive Moment Estimation) optimizer is used across all models, with a learning rate of 0.001 and a batch size of 30. SoftMax classifier is employed for predicting the respective image classes. A comparison is made with the accuracy of the chosen pretrained models. The results demonstrate that our fine-tuned models exhibit higher accuracy in both training and testing, as well as overall accuracy. The proposed fine-tuned InceptionV3 and Xception models achieve the highest accuracies of 99.25% and 99.16%, respectively, for the GHIM10K and Plant seedling datasets.

Keywords: Multiclass image classification, Deep learning, Convolutional neural networks, Transfer learning, Fine-tuning.

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Introduction

According to the data, Deep learning derived from traditional artificial neural networks has received more academic and industrial attention in recent years. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have become increasingly popular in the field of image understanding, representing a prominent deep learning technique. CNN has been widely employed and has demonstrated promising results, particularly in image recognition [1],[2],[3]. One of the most significant advantages of using a CNN is that it does not require manual feature extraction, making it resistant to new datasets. CNN has been utilized as a fundamental image categorization method since its introduction approximately two decades ago [4]. Towards enhancing classification accuracy, image classifying research has seen the advancement of computer vision algorithms from first-order moments to customized features and end-to-end machine learning techniques. Image classification and image analysis applications are used in a variety of disciplines, including military and civil fields, face recognition, textile image analysis, automatic illness diagnosis, geographic mapping, and video processing [5][6][7]. Deep learning has advanced rapidly in the last decade, with *Hinton et al.* [8] introducing an efficient weight initialization method and *Talbar et al.*[9] presenting supervised learning for texture classification. *Ojhalo et al.* [10] introduced local binary patterns (LBP) to extract local neighborhood variables, but they were unable to extract directional information. *Lowe et al.* [11] has introduced the Scale-Invariant Feature Transform (SIFT) to identify scale-invariant interest points, and *Bay et al.* [12] developed Speeded-Up Robust Features (SURF) to minimize the computational cost of SIFT for images classification and other computer vision applications.

The above-mentioned feature descriptors have been witnessed in the expansion of the digital picture library and the emergence of big-scale datasets. Substantial inter-class diversity in image classes, traditional features underperform in big-scale databases. Researchers have employed CNN feature extraction in various applications because of its robustness. It was first proposed in the 1960s. *Hubel and Wiesel* discovered for the very first moment in their investigations of cat visual cortex cells found neurons inside the visual cortex appeared sensitive towards moving edges, and they developed the idea of "receptive field"[13]. The idea of "receptive field" was afterward included in CNN development. "Neocognitron"[14] was the first neural network built on local connection with hierarchical structure interconnected neurons and was mainly used to recognize handwritten digits. Until the ImageNet competition of 2012 [15], when its full potential was found, a breakthrough set of revolutionary achievements in image classification, thanks to the efficient utilization of graphics processing units, rectifying linear units, innovative dropout regularization with powerful data augmentation. *Alex et al.* [16] proposed an evolving CNN architecture called AlexNet, which resulted in a victory in the ImageNet competition in 2012. Since then, more studies have focused on improving CNN architecture, with AlexNet achieving an accuracy ratio of 84.7% using deep learning in 2012 and 97.3% in 2017.

Deeper convolution architectures were developed by researchers to increase classification accuracy to outperform human visual perception even further. *Simonyan et al.* [17] introduced a model known as VGG to investigate how the depth of a convolutional network affects its accuracy in a large-scale image recognition circumstance. VGG's essential contribution is a detailed examination of networks on increasing depth utilizing an architecture with extremely tiny (3×3) convolution filters. Expanding the depth to 16 to 19 weight layers greatly improves the prior-art structure. InceptionV3[18] is a network architecture built on AlexNet revisions and can identify 1000 classes with a top 5 error ratio of 3.5% and a top 1 error identifying ratio of 17.3%. It maintains memory more effectively than other network models and offers significant benefits over the preceding ones. Microsoft announced "Deep Residual Learning"[19] to address the vanishing gradient issue [20] and the degradation [21] of convolutional neural networks. Xception [22] architecture was built on many essential aspects, such as convolution operation, depth-wise separable layer, function of inception, and residual interconnections. Xception surpasses InceptionV3 moderately but significantly on a larger image database, with a top-1 prediction error of 21.0%.

Furthermore, the significant improvement in deep CNN representing capabilities is achieved by architectural improvements. *Rehman et al.* [23] proposed using multiple convolutional neural network architectures (AlexNet,

GoogLeNet, and VGGNet) to classify brain tumors utilizing transfer learning [24]. The fine-tuned VGGNet architecture achieved the highest classification accuracy of close to 98.69%. Prateek et al. [25] propose a fully automated diagnostic device based on a neural network system which is a conventional InceptionV3 model plus additional five layers added with the aid of transfer learning to improve model performance achieved mean accuracy 90.16%. Authors Amsa et al. [26], Neha Sharma et al. [27], and Reddy et al. [28] attempt to fine-tune ResNet50 for satellite and scene image classification, CIFAR10 and CIFAR100 datasets classification, and classification of malaria cell-image, with an accuracy of 97%, 59.82%, and 78.10%, 95%, respectively. Author M. Rahimzadeh et al. [29] proposed an approach based on the concatenation using Xception and Resnet50V2, average accuracy was obtained 91.4%. Author Natina Jinsakul et al. [30] suggested an Xception-based model with the Swish Activation Function improving accuracy of up to 98.99% in classifying among two classes and 91.48% for classifying into three classes. Author Wu et al. [31] presented a transfer learning approach for scene classification based on Xception and compared its performance with the InceptionV3 model. Transfer learning based on InceptionV3 and Xception achieved 91.81% and 91.20% accuracy, respectively. Xiao et al. [32] selected inceptionV3, Resnet50, and Xception to solve the challenge of distinguishing benign cysts against malignant tumors using breast ultrasound (BUS) pictures. Transfer learning based InceptionV3 obtained the greatest performance, with 85.13% accuracy and an AUC of 0.91. Classification model developed derived from deep extracting features gained 89.44% accuracy. Wen et al. [33] proposed a pre-trained VGG19 feature extractor to acquire the features of transformed pictures, and a SoftMax classifier was trained upon that features. The ultimate accuracy rate of TCNN was 99.175%, model training time was just about 200 seconds. Xiao et al. [34] presented a deep learning-based security detection system that employs machine vision rather than manual monitoring. Three fully connected layers are simplified using the transfer learning approach into one flat layer plus two fully connected layers with lower parameters. A two-label SoftMax classifier replaces the pre-trained model's layer of SoftMax classification. The precision of recognizing employees without masks was 96.82%, and recall was 94.07%. Xia et al. [35] suggested a transfer learning approach to retraining the flower categories databases, significantly increasing flower recognition accuracy on the Oxford-17 flower database. achieved accuracy of 95%, while on the Oxford-102 flower dataset classification accuracy of 94%.

Having emerged as the most powerful approach for image classification, training CNN needs massive amounts of data, computing infrastructure, and time consumption. Many machine learning algorithms are only effective when the training and test data come from the same feature space and distribution. Once the distribution shifts, most models should be recreated from zero, utilizing freshly gathered training data. Low-quality input photos had a significant impact on the performance of the current popular convolutional network model. The classification accuracy will be substantially improved by improving image quality; generalization problem in supervised machine learning called overfitting occurs when a model does not generalize properly from input data to validation data. Accuracy of some convolutional neural networks is not adequate. To learn any feature out of an image, only the best quality picture is essential, but literature analysis reveals that obtaining a perfect database is hard. For multiclass image classification in several application domains, deep learning algorithms based on convolutional neural networks provide many benefits and conveniences. Pre-trained networks have a higher ability since they have been trained on large-scale pictures for a large class label. In such circumstances, knowledge transfer or transfer learning between task domains will be beneficial. Thus, the goal of this research is (1) to study the different image classification CNN model, as well as prospective improvements through proposed architectural modification for multiclass image classification using transfer learning to fine-tuning, (2) to compare the performance with the chosen pre-trained models' accuracy, also with the literature accuracy (3) overcome generalization problem and check robustness during testing providing entirely unseen samples of each class of image, (4) to study the necessity of decreased loss function, (5) demonstrate the easiness with which the deep learning algorithm can be implemented.

2. Dataset

In our experiment, publicly available multiclass dataset named GHIM10K and plant seedling dataset were used. Author *Guang-Hai Liu* [36] gathered each photograph contained within this dataset either from relevant websites or through a camera. Included a total combination of 10,000 natural landscape photographs, a variety of elements examples instance fireworks display, castle, automobile, flowers and so on. Overall exist a total of twenty categories. Its resolution is either 300×400 or 400×300. A maximum of 500 JPEG photos are featured under each class shown in Fig. 1. The dataset was split into training and testing in a balanced way using a python library called split-folders. each training class contains 400 images and each testing class contains 100 images.

Fig. 1: Random specimens from each category of GHIM10K dataset

The Plant Seedlings [37] database was originally prepared by the Aarhus University Flakkebjerg Experimental Laboratory through collaboration between the University of Southern Denmark as well as Aarhus University. The Plant Seedlings Dataset includes photographs of roughly 960 unique plants representing twelve diverse species across diverse periods of growth. It comprises primarily annotated RGB photographs throughout PNG type having overall physical resolution of roughly 10 pixels each millimeter. Because the image allocation within every class differed, this dataset was splited across seventy percent training as well as thirty percent testing. There are approximately 3794 photographs within the training dataset and 956 photographs within the testing dataset. A sample from each class has shown in Fig 2.

Fig. 2: Random specimens from each category of Plant Seedlings dataset

3. Basic Methods

Throughout the multiclass image classification process, the CNN framework plays a vital role in accurately categorizing the images based on their diverse types and classes. In this study, deep learning models were utilized for multiclass image classification. Prior to fed images to a classification algorithm, every single image contained in the dataset was preprocessed, augmented, and artificially enhanced as well as segmented into training and testing. Every convolution neural network is generally separated into three parts, input layer, feature extractor section, and classification section; from each pre-trained model, the classification section was eliminated and replaced with our proposed classification section. After the fine-tuning based on the obtained classification accuracy, two models were proposed; InceptionV3 for GHIM10k dataset and Xception for Plant seedling dataset, as the classification performance is subject to the selection of appropriate models based on the type of datasets working with. During the model training process of transfer learning pre-trained models' weights were freeze and were unfreeze some layers weights during fine-tuning process. Seventeen initial epochs for transfer learning and twenty epochs during fine-tuning were used. Fine-tuning epochs starts from the end of transfer learning epochs rather than starting from the beginning. All CNN models were built on Google colab notebook with the assistance of Keras library and TensorFlow. Overall schematic flow chart of the methodology is presented in Fig.3. Details of CNN describe in section 3.1.

Fig. 3: Overall schematic processed for multiclass image classification

3.1. Convolutional neural networks framework

In an end-to-end way, a DCNN (Deep Convolutional Neural Networks) dynamically learns the best feature from sources. DCNNs learn to construct the anticipated distribution of image class in the image classification problem by extracting features from an input picture. To generate outputs, an artificial neuron of neural networks computes the weighted mean of a bunch of input data and applies a non-linearity activation equation to it [38]. Both inputs and

outputs of a neural network are frequently expressed either as a vector or a vector array. Hidden layers of a neural network outcomes feature vectors. An artificial neural network consists of a collection of neurons that are linked together. Layers of a neural network are a group of neurons located at about the same depth as the inputs. Neural networks include an input layer, a bunch of hidden layers, and an output layer. Neural net that consists of one or more hidden units, designated as deep neural networks. Convolutional neural nets are one type of deeper artificial neural network which is used to categorize images and recognize objects among scenarios.

Images are observed and analyzed as tensors by CNNs. Tensors are multidimensional matrices of variables. Conventional neural networks include an input neural layer, an output neural layer, and multiple hidden layers in between. When an input picture goes throughout the hidden layers of CNN, it is subjected to three separate operations namely convolution layers featuring specific filters, pooling layers, as well as a rectifying linear unit known as ReLU. Furthermore, among these layers, a procedure known as normalization is used. These three steps are performed several times throughout the hidden layers, with each layer gaining knowledge to identify a unique characteristic.

A convolutional neural network is illustrated in Fig. 4 as a schematic diagram with several hierarchical layers such as input layer, feature extraction layers including convolution and max pooling layer, classification layers with fully interconnected layers. The very first layer of a CNN is commonly the convolution layer, which creates feature maps utilizing filters. Weight values are confined to be identical for all neurons inside a feature map. Furthermore, the weights of multiple feature maps inside the identical convolutional layer vary, allowing numerous characteristics to be extracted at one location. Brief architectural description of chosen VGG19, ResNet50, Inception and Xception is given below.

3.1.1. VGG 19

The VGG19[17] architecture is constructed with five convolutional layer units and three fully connected layers. It is an extended version of the VGG framework, consisting of a total of 19 layers. The VGG19 model includes sixteen convolutional layers, three fully connected layers, five max pooling layers, and one SoftMax classification layer. In VGG19, 3x3 filters with a stride and padding of 1 are extensively utilized, along with 2x2 max-pooling layers with a stride of 2. The input for the VGG19 model is a three-channel image represented by the dimensions 224x224x3. After each convolutional layer, followed by a max-pooling layer, the input image size reduces to 112x112, 56x56, 28x28, 14x14, and eventually 7x7.

Fig. 4: A conventional framework of convolutional neural network

3.1.2. ResNet50

The ResNet 50[19] CNN model is a residual framework composed of 50 layers. It takes an input image size of 224x224x3. The distinguishing feature of the ResNet architecture is the presence of identity connections between layers. Dashed and curved lines indicate that the convolution operation within the Residual learning Block is performed with a stride of 2, resulting in a 50% reduction in the input image dimensions in both height and width, while doubling the channel width. The ResNet50 model is organized into four stages. In the initial convolution and max-pooling layers, 7x7 and

3×3 kernel parameters are used, respectively. The network then proceeds to Phase 1, which comprises three Residual learning blocks, each consisting of three layers. These layers are stacked on top of each other, including a 1×1, 3×3, and 1×1 convolutional layer. In these three Residual learning blocks of Phase 1, the employed kernels for the convolution operation are 64, 64, and 256, respectively. ResNet, with its residual learning blocks, can be extended to architectures exceeding 100 or even 1000 layers.

3.1.3. Inception V3

InceptionV3[18], developed by Google, is a CNN framework widely used in deep learning strategies for image recognition. The architecture of InceptionV3 has undergone various enhancements to improve its performance and flexibility. These enhancements include factorized convolutional techniques, regularization techniques, dimension reduction techniques, and parallel computations. The core concept of InceptionV3, known as V1, utilizes 1×1, 3×3, and 5×5 convolutions, along with a max pooling layer. To reduce computational complexity, the initial 5×5 convolutions are replaced with two consecutive 3×3 convolutions. This approach allows larger convolutions to be represented by smaller convolution layers. Asymmetric convolutions, denoted as $n \times 1$, are also employed to enhance efficiency. A 3×3 convolution is replaced with a 1×3 convolution followed by a 3×1 convolution. InceptionV3 incorporates an auxiliary classifier, which is a mini CNN network inserted between layers during training. This auxiliary classifier aids in regularizing the primary CNN network's losses. Pooling methods are often used for lower grid dimensions. In InceptionV3, this strategy is achieved by concatenating two parallel units consisting of a convolutional layer and a pooling layer. Additionally, a batch normalization layer is added as a functional regularizer between the auxiliary classifier and the fully connected convolutional layer in the InceptionV3 model. By default, InceptionV3 expects color images as input and has an input size of 299×299.

3.1.4. Xception

The Xception framework, introduced in the paper [22], incorporates several key components, including convolutional layers, depth-wise separable convolution layers, inception units, and residual links. Xception can be considered an advanced version of the Inception framework that utilizes a specific type of convolution operation called depth-wise separable convolution. The Xception module is known for its high resilience compared to the Inception module. During data acquisition, a single 1×1 convolution feature is generated followed by an independent convolution feature of size 3×3. These features are then concatenated after being sorted into non-overlapping regions within their respective destination feeds. The use of depth-wise separable layers reduces the computational complexity and the number of parameters in the framework across the spatial size and depth of the color channels. This is achieved by separating the conventional convolution operation into a depth-wise convolution followed by a point-wise convolution using a 1×1 convolutional filter. The Xception architecture adopts the initial ResNet network technique of using residual blocks but with modifications. It consists of thirty-six convolutional layers, and the input image is expected to have dimensions of 299×299×3. The entrance flow starts with the first unit, which includes two convolutional layers with kernel sizes of 2 and 3×3, respectively, with 32 and 64 filters. The second to fourth units have separable convolutional filters of sizes 128, 256, and 728, respectively, with the same kernel size. The initial entrance flow generates a feature map of size 19×19×728. This feature map is then iterated through eight cycles in the middle flow, where filters of size 728 are used. In the exit flow, separable convolutions with 728 and 1024 filters are employed. The final module consists of separable convolutions with 1536 and 2048 filters.

3.2. Transfer Learning

Domains and tasks are used to describe transfer learning. Domain D being comprised on two portions: basic feature area x plus initial minimal probabilistic allocation $P(X)$, where $X = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\} \in x$. Having any distinct domain $D = \{X, P(X)\}$, Any task being comprised with two portions: its labeling area y plus its goal prediction equation $f: x \rightarrow y$. Its function f gets utilized for forecast exact label $f(x)$ of a fresh entity x . one such task, marked via $\tau = \{y, f(x)\}$. gets learnt through training samples composed with pairings $\{x_i, y_i\}$, wherein, $x_i \in X$ also $y_i \in y$. Having one source domain D_s

as well as any having to learn task τ_s , and any goal domain D_T as well as any having to learn task τ_T , wherein $D_s \neq D_T$, alternatively $\tau_s \neq \tau_T$, transfer learning [39] intends to aid throughout its learning towards goal prediction function $f_T(\cdot)$ within D_T employing information from D_s also τ_s .

3.3. Fine tuning

Fine-tuning, as described in the paper [40], refers to the process of taking an existing network that has been developed using a large annotated database for a different task and using it as a starting point for training a new network. Pre-trained networks can serve as a valuable resource for various computer vision applications, either as a basic feature extractor or as a foundation for transfer learning. Rather than training a network from scratch, fine-tuning involves unfreezing the entire pre-trained network and retraining it on new samples with relatively small learning rates. By progressively applying the features learned by the pre-trained network to new samples, the fine-tuning approach has the potential to achieve significant success. This allows the network to adapt its learned representations to the specific characteristics of the new dataset or task, while still benefiting from the knowledge and features learned from the original task. Fine-tuning is an effective strategy for leveraging pre-trained networks and transferring their knowledge to new domains or tasks, providing a valuable shortcut in training deep neural networks for computer vision applications. Assuming one Network containing L number of layers, its final three of which being completely linked layers. Furthermore, allow α_l signify its learning percentage for a l^{th} layer. Through defining $\alpha_l = 0$ for $l \neq L$, possible to fine-tune just its rearmost layer. One such scale fine-tuning coincides towards teaching one regression classifier along its characteristics obtained through layer $L-1$. Similarly, its rearmost two levels respectively fine-tuned through configuring $\alpha_l = 0$ for $l \neq L, L-1$. One such extended fine-tuning equivalent to one disguised layer training, that becomes equivalent teaching one regression classifier along its characteristics obtained through layer $L-2$. tuning levels $L, L-1$, as well as $L-2$ is analogous to two disguised layer training. Tuning its rearmost couple layers is called shallow tuning, tuning every layer is regarded to deep tuning.

4. Proposed method

This study consists primarily of several CNN model designs and transfer learning strategies in conjunction with fine-tuning to increase the accuracy of multiclass image classification. Pre-trained model's classifier section was replaced with a global average pooling layer, flatten layers, 0.5 dropout layers, and new dense layers that include the number of classes for each dataset and the SoftMax classifier for each model as shown in Fig. 5.

After the CNN model is designed and the weights are initialized, the model is compiled using *model.compile* techniques, pre-trained models' layers with our newly added layers and fed the data into CNN model using the *model.fit_generator* method during transfer learning and fine-tuning process. During the finetuning process, relative layers were unfrozen and re-trained it with a learning rate of 0.001 as shown in Fig. 6. Models were trained using the optimizer across a range of epochs, constant learning rates, also with constant batch sizes. *categorical_crossentropy* along with metrics accuracy were used to determine the loss function.

Early stopping function was used in our model, that keep tracking the loss function during validation period, and if the loss isn't decreed more than 3 epochs, it stop the training and save the best model; which helps to prevent overfitting the CNN model as well. During the training process testing data was used as validation data. *model.evaluate_generator* was used for evaluate model's accuracy and loss; which is training and testing loss and accuracy. *model.predict_generator* was configured to get classification report using the precision, recall and f1-score, through confusion matrixes.

4.1. Preprocessing

Artificial neural networking frameworks typically do not directly understand or process unprocessed inputs such as text files, encoded JPEG photographs, or CSV files. These inputs need to undergo computational conversion and preprocessing before they can be fed into the neural network for analysis. For example, in the case of images, a common preprocessing step is to convert the images to the BGR (Blue-Green-Red) color space, which is commonly used in

computer vision tasks. Additionally, the pixel values of each color channel are typically zero-centered with respect to the mean values of the primary ImageNet database, without any scaling operation.

Fig.5: Optimization operation of pre-trained model

Fig. 6: Illustration of overall fine-tuning process

This means that the mean value of each color channel is subtracted from the corresponding pixel values. Furthermore, after zero-centering, the pixel values are often normalized or rescaled to a specific range. It is common to scale the pixel values to lie within the range of -1 to 1. This rescaling ensures that the input values are within a suitable range for the neural network to process effectively. By performing these preprocessing steps, the raw inputs such as text files, JPEG photographs, or CSV files can be transformed into a format that artificial neural networks can understand and process effectively for various tasks, including image classification, object detection, and natural language processing. This is accomplished by

$$X' = X - \mu$$

In which normalized data denotes through X' , source data indicates through X , as well as μ represents the mean vector throughout the entire X' features. Several number of data augmentation approaches were employed, which enable transformed images to get created from original photograph with minimal processing, minimizing the need for those transformed images being keep stored on memory. Cropping, rotations, flips, translations, as well as various data augmentation operations adopted for our classification task. Table 1 illustrates additional augmentation technique that was done prior to fitting data further onto CNN architecture. As illustrated in Fig.7, every single picture passes via augmentation techniques modifications. From *keras.preprocessing.image* using *ImageDataGenerator* data augmentation has done for our task. Overall effectiveness of a CNN generally linearly proportional with its quality of input data employed when train a convolutional network system. thus, dataset quality was upgraded prior to fitting as input to classification algorithm. For plant dataset, picture color, contrast and sharpness were enhanced employing *PIL* image library using *ImageEnhance* feature as shown in Fig. 8 and the enhancement value given in Table 2. As the GHIM dataset already consist of high-quality images therefor it only for plant seedling dataset.

Table 1 Data augmentation details

Standard procedures	Value
Rotation_range	40
Width_shift_range	0.2
Height_shift_range	0.2
Shear_range	0.2
Zoom_range	0.2
Channel_shift_range	10
Horizontal_flip	True
Fill_mode	Nearest

Table 2 Image enhancement details

Standard procedures	Value
ImageEnhance.Color	1.35
ImageEnhance.Contrast	1.45
ImageEnhance.Sharpness	2.5

Fig. 7: Visual representation of augmented data

Fig. 8: Visualization of artificially enhance data for plant dataset

4.2. Inception V3

The InceptionV3 model was modified and fine-tuned specifically for the GHIM10K dataset classification task. Some layers of the pre-trained InceptionV3 model were optimized to address the generalization problem and improve overall loss function, leading to an increase in accuracy. Table 3 provides details of the modified structure of InceptionV3 for the GHIM10K dataset classification task. During the transfer learning stage, all layers of the model were configured as non-trainable, meaning their weights were frozen. This resulted in the transfer learning stage achieving accuracy equivalent to the pre-trained model's accuracy. During the fine-tuning process, starting from the conv2d_93 layer, the layers were configured as trainable. This allowed these layers to be further optimized and adjusted based on the GHIM10K dataset. The total number of parameters in the modified InceptionV3 model for the GHIM10K dataset classification was 21,843,764. Out of these parameters, 434,708 were trainable parameters, meaning their weights were adjusted during the fine-tuning process, while 21,409,056 parameters were non-trainable, representing the frozen weights from the pre-trained model.

4.3. Xception

The Xception model was proposed and modified for the plant seedling dataset classification task, using similar optimization techniques as mentioned earlier. In addition to the modifications, an extra dense layer with 512 units and a ReLU activation function was added after the flatten layer. This additional dense layer helps in capturing more complex patterns and features from the extracted representations. The proposed structure of the modified Xception model for the plant seedling dataset classification can be found in Figure 9. During the fine-tuning process, the layers were configured as trainable starting from the block14_sepconv2 layer. This allows the model to fine-tune and adjust the weights of these layers based on the plant seedling dataset. In terms of the total number of parameters, the modified Xception model for the plant seedling dataset classification has 21,916,724 parameters. Out of these, 4,218,892 parameters are trainable, meaning their weights are adjusted during the fine-tuning process, while 17,697,832 parameters are non-trainable, representing the frozen weights from the pre-trained model.

4.4. Dropout regularization

Probably amongst all regularization techniques its foremost prominent procedure in regularization is termed dropout. Overfitting is one vital concern which must get addressed, since larger neural nets remain challenging both trained also deploy throughout testing. Dropout represents one technique aimed towards overcoming such difficulties. Dropout [41] describes one approach involving eliminating neurons within any neural net over randomly having overall likelihood ratio $q = 1 - p$. All individual neuron's receiving as well as departing interconnections get disregarded once neuron gets dropped completely. One purpose by eliminating neurons entirely randomly aims simply allow individual neuron will grasp things essential upon its individual not focusing excessively onto neighboring neurons for correct its flaws. In our experiment, we use dropout by 0.5, before classification layer for each model.

Table 3 Inception V3 Structure details

Type	patch size/stride	input size
Conv	3×3/2	229×229×3
Conv	3×3/1	149×149×3
conv padded	3×3/1	147×147×32
pool	3×3/2	147×147×64
conv	3×3/1	73×73×64
conv	3×3/2	71×71×80

Type	patch size/stride	input size
conv	3×3/1	35×35×192
3×Inception	Three modules	35×35×288
5×Inception	Five modules	17×17×768
2×Inception	Two modules	8×8×1280

Global average pool, Flatten, Dropout, 20-d fc (SoftMax)

Fig. 9: Architecture of proposed Xception model

4.5. Optimization techniques

4.5.1. Adaptive Moment Estimation (Adam)

The cross-entropy function is commonly used to estimate the loss in deep neural networks. In our study, our main objective is to enhance accuracy by reducing the loss function. Optimization algorithms are employed to effectively decrease the loss function. Throughout our research, we utilized the Adam optimizer to minimize the overall loss function. Adam optimizer incorporates Adaptive Moment Estimation [42], which is a functional optimization technique that estimates adaptable learning rates for each parameter in the system. It combines the capabilities of Momentum and RMSprop. These following gets used to update its weights for such Adam optimizer:

$$w_t^i = w_{t-1}^i - \frac{\eta}{\sqrt{\hat{v}_t} + \epsilon} \cdot \hat{m}_t$$

$$\hat{m}_t = \frac{m_t}{1 - \beta_1^t}, \quad \hat{v}_t = \frac{v_t}{1 - \beta_2^t}, \quad m_t = \beta_1 m_{t-1} + (1 - \beta_1) \frac{\partial L}{\partial w_t},$$

$$v_t = \beta_2 v_{t-1} + (1 - \beta_2) \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial w_t} \right]^2 \text{ and } \frac{\partial L}{\partial w_t} = \nabla_w C(w_t; x^{(B)}; y^{(B)})$$

wherein $\beta_i \in [0, 1]$ indicates how considerable information will wanted from its earlier iteration, m_t represents its initial momentum, which represents individual gradients' moving mean, as well as v_t represents its secondary momentum, which represent the quadratic gradients' moving mean. Its bias-corrected initial also secondary momentums represent by $\hat{m}_t$ as well as $\hat{v}_t$, respectively.

4.5.2. Learning rate

The learning rate is a crucial tunable parameter in any optimization algorithm as it determines the step size taken during each iteration to minimize the overall loss function. Achieving optimal results often involves additional training epochs with a relatively lower learning rate, as a higher learning rate may lead to an overestimation of the ideal outcome. Effective training of a neural network for successful image classification can be achieved by employing an optimization method that decreases the non-convex loss function $L(\theta)$.

$$\arg \min_{\theta \in \mathbb{R}} L(\theta); L(\theta) = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M L_i(\theta)$$

wherein $L(\theta)$ indicates its overall loss during training photograph $L_i(\theta)$ across all dataset while M indicates image database size. In our experiment learning rate 0.001 was used.

4.5.3. Batch size

Batch size is another hyperparameter that requires tuning. It determines the total number of photographs used for training our networks within each epoch. If this hyperparameter is set too high, the model may take an excessively long time to reach convergence without significant improvement in accuracy. On the other hand, if it is set too low, the neural system may oscillate and fail to achieve satisfactory accuracy. Consequently, a batch size of 32 was chosen as the optimal configuration.

5. Results

According to the task requirement towards ultimate goal of reducing training and testing loss, Adam optimizer was adopted and tuned hyperparameters such as learning rate and batch size; in order to evaluate its disparity among legitimate as well as anticipated values, generated by SoftMax function; cross entropy loss function of the aforementioned likelihood $p \in \{0,1\}$ was used; throughout multiclass classifying concerns broadly employed, emits its performance under likelihood function $p, y \in \mathbb{R}^N$, in which p represents its likelihood from every outcome from class while y represents its desirable result. statistical likelihood from every class acquired as follows:

$$p_i = \frac{e^{\alpha_i}}{\sum_{k=1}^N e^{\alpha_k}}$$

In which N signifies output layer neuron count; e^{a_i} signifies every result derived through prior layer, that fulfill none of class probabilities. Eventually, cross-entropy loss described follows:

$$H(p, y) = - \sum_i y'_i \log(y_i)$$

In which y represents forecasted value, y'_i represents true value, i represents classes count.

Proposed multiclass image classification framework's potency is assessed through determining evaluation metrics relying on multiple key aspects which utilized to evaluate the classification algorithm. An ideal classifier contains matrices, just diagonal values but also has zero values for remaining aspects. A confusion matrix gets generated only after classification operation to extract actual as well as predicted values. Multiclass image classification model's performance was evaluated relying on Precision, Recall, F1-score and Accuracy of overall each model.

Precision: Precision is defined as the proportion of appropriately classified images out of overall classified images. It is calculated by using the following equation:

$$P = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

Recall: Recall represents the ratio of appropriately classified images in relation to datasets related images count. Recall represent computationally as:

$$R = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

F1 score: Also recognized as F measure, represent assessment for test accuracy. It symbolizes a weighted sum of accuracy and recall.

$$F1 = \frac{2 \times P \times R}{P + R}$$

Accuracy: It encompasses a classifier's overall appropriate predictions count. To calculate it, use the equation below.

$$A = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + FP + FN + TN}$$

VGG 19, ResNet 50, Inception V3, Xception models fine-tuning accuracy 99%, 99.15%, 99.25%, 99.1% and 93%, 84.4%, 92.6%, 99.16% for GHIM and plant seedling dataset respectively. The accuracy increases as well as model's loss decrease through proposed fine-tuning process after modified the pre-trained model using transfer learning approach as shown in Table 4. Table 5 summarize all model's accuracy, precision, recall and F-1 score. Experiment was conducted using publicly available dataset named GHIM10K and plant seedling dataset. As shown in Fig. 10 the height accuracy was obtained is 99.25% and 99.16% for GHIM and plant seedling dataset respectively, thus these two models was proposed. Modified Inception v3, Xception class wise precision accuracy are 100% within 12 class and 7 class for GHIM and plant seedling dataset respectively. Overall precision, recall, F1 score is 99.25% and 99.16% for GHIM10K dataset and plant dataset respectively obtained through proposed models which is better than the other models. Proposed model's confusion matrixes have given in Fig. 11, 12 respectively.

Comparing to the model's overall accuracy before and after fine-tuned, experiment results shows that accuracy improved from 97.55% to 99.25%; and 76.98% to 99.16% for GHIM dataset and plant dataset respectively through their respective proposed model. Experiments graph verify that there is no major underfitting or overfitting issues appears of proposed models have been shown in figure 13, 14 respectively. Several authors have used the GHIM and plant seedling dataset in their studies. The authors H. A. Elnemr [43], Ofori et al. [44], Gupta et al. [45], Namratha Makanapura et al. [46] utilized plant seedling dataset and Authors Ying Liu et al. [47], Ying Liu et al. [48] used GHIM10k dataset in their research and Table 6 and Table 7 prove that the result obtained by proposed method is better than others.

Table 4 classification report of all models

Dataset	Model	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Accuracy
GHIM dataset	VGG 19	.9875	.9875	.9875	.99
plant seedlings	VGG 19	.9325	.9225	.9315	.93
GHIM dataset	ResNet 50	.9915	.9915	.9915	.9915
plant seedlings	ResNet 50	.8441	.8441	.8441	.8441
GHIM dataset	Inception V3	.9925	.9925	.9925	.9925
plant seedlings	Inception V3	.9267	.9267	.9267	.9267
GHIM dataset	Xception	.991	.991	.991	.991
plant seedlings	Xception	.9916	.9916	.9916	.9916

Table 5 All model accuracy and losses

Dataset	Model	Train Acc	Train loss	Test Acc	Test loss
GHIM dataset	VGG-19 TL	0.929	0.228	0.951	0.176
	VGG-19 FT	0.991	0.027	0.989	0.049
plant seedlings	VGG-19 TL	0.484	1.539	0.488	1.594
	VGG-19 FT	0.960	0.138	0.932	0.178
GHIM dataset	ResNet-50 TL	0.976	0.079	0.987	0.047
	ResNet-50 FT	0.992	0.030	0.991	0.036
plant seedlings	ResNet-50 TL	0.759	0.869	0.697	0.812
	ResNet-50 FT	0.899	0.338	0.844	0.413
GHIM dataset	Inception-V3 TL	0.966	0.121	0.976	0.093
	Inception-V3 FT	0.994	0.025	0.992	0.028
plant seedlings	Inception-V3 TL	0.639	1.258	0.554	1.411
	Inception-V3 FT	0.944	0.194	0.924	0.228
GHIM dataset	Xception TL	0.968	0.133	0.975	0.116
	Xception FT	0.996	0.012	0.991	0.027
plant seedlings	Xception TL	0.813	0.588	0.766	0.674
	Xception FT	0.995	0.011	0.991	0.032

Note: TL stands for transfer learning, FT stands for fine-tuning.

Fig. 10: Model accuracy for GHIM and plant seedling dataset

Additionally, from Table 5, training and testing accuracy is satisfactory and the model loss is less than the maximum allowable loss, which meets the requirements for multiclass image classification framework.

Fig. 11: Inception V3 Confusion matrix during fine tuning process for GHIM dataset

Fig. 12: Xception model Confusion matrix during fine tuning process for plant dataset

Fig. 13: Experiments graph of Inception V3 model for GHIM dataset

Fig. 14: Experiments graph of Xception model for plant seedling dataset

Table 6 Comparison of plant seedling dataset accuracy with other literature

Method	Model	Accuracy
[74]	CNN	94.38%.
[75]	ResNet152V2	92.93%
[76]	ResNet50	95.23%.
[77]	EfficientNetB0	96.52%
Proposed framework	Xception	99.16%

Table 7 Comparison of GHIM-10K dataset accuracy with other literature

Method	Model	Accuracy
[78]	VGG-f	94.61%
[79]	VGG-VD16	98.40%
Proposed framework	Inception V3	99.25%

6. Conclusion

This article studied the application of various convolutional neural network in the multiclass image classification system and proposed two optimized CNN model for chosen datasets. It focuses on improving the corresponding model's accuracy, as well as reducing the loss during training and testing using the transfer learning approach. Image enhancement, mean subtraction, data augmentation, dropout regularization, early stopping function, and hyper-parameters like learning rate batch size are analyzed. Pre-trained trained model is optimized using global average pooling layer, dropout layer, flatten layer and newly added dense layer incorporate with SoftMax classification layer. Fine-tuning method is studied, based on the fine-tuning approach layers weight from the pre-trained model is updated. Results show that our fine-tuned model accuracy is higher in terms of training and testing as well as model's overall accuracy. This shows that the suggested approach is well suited for use in multiclass image classification applications. Based on the research in this article, future research from the following aspects: In future, the convolutional neural network studied in this research, fine-tuned using transfer learning approach might be beneficial for object recognition task, can be employed in different research; according to the requirement the model can be selected. Towards the ultimate classification accuracy Inception V3 and Xception convolutional neural network can be merge together, automatic selection of finetuning layers for different datasets and obtain the best trainable parameters, thereby achieving better classification accuracy. The real-time aspect of image recognition framework can be build using our fined-tuned model and demonstrated the real time recognition accuracy.

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